

De-architecturing Architecture

Architecture as an ongoing
process between decay and
renovation.

Lars Fischer

common room

In 1972 the American artist Robert Smithson gave a slide lecture at the architecture faculty of the University of Utah. In this lecture Smithson describes the Hotel Palenque in Mexico, on the surface a dilapidated and unremarkable building. Smithson's meandering narration of the slides however relates the building as the intriguing process of continued decay and renovation, situating the hotel as a found object in a continuum of larger timescales exposed to the forces of what he calls entropy.

Entropy, generally understood as degradation into disorder, is a topic that had fascinated Smithson. He related the state of entropy to multiple fields, from geology or economy to systems theory, however he never clearly explicated the theory. For Smithson the notion of continuous change was significant, a change towards increased disorder, with time always moving forwards. Yet this movement towards decay and dissolution was for him also generative and emancipative. Smithson sought to communicate these entropic processes that define our environment in an attempt at displaying the potentials, at making entropy visible.¹

Smithson's art, especially in his land art projects, is directed at viewing and expressing processes, both natural and industrial, that alter and shape our environment. The sites he engaged with were often overlooked, abandoned or remote, sites of geological formations, postindustrial detritus, or suburban sprawl. Smithson's

1 Robert Smithson, "Entropy Made Visible (1973). Interview with Alison Sky," in Robert Smithson. *The Collected Writings*, ed. Jack Flam (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1996), 301–9.

work, his interventions in these sites are a translation of his observations, making the processes of change, of erosion and destruction, legible, revealing the aspect of time and expressing a potentiality, which these processes and sites offer. In relating these conditions Smithson goes beyond

Robert Smithson, *Hotel Palenque* 1969-72, thirty-one chromogenic-development slides and audio recording, collection Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum, New York. © Estate of Robert Smithson.

typical images of landscape or architecture, of finished and finite scenes, escaping the conventional aesthetic perceptions of our environment. Smithson describes an aesthetic not based on completion, but on transformation

and dissolution, not on beauty, but on decay and demolition. He applies a different understanding of destruction that sees a certain anticipation in the degraded, in natural and geological processes as well as the deconstructed detritus of modernism. These scenes for him are imbued with possibility, embedded in time, linked to a history remembered but more importantly to a future imagined.

Smithson's fascination with the scenes of entropic process is reflected both in the way he perceives his surroundings and the manner in which he conveys these observations and perceptions. His texts, rather than merely accompanying the physical components, are an integral part of the work itself. They take the form not of descriptive texts but rather of narration, in an often convoluted manner, center-less with various tangents and manifold interpretations, but always moving forward, relating entropic change in form and content. Text and narration allow Smithson to reveal processes that aren't communicable through pictorial means. He makes associations to distant sites and events as well as projects and speculates on future unknown potentials not yet manifested, describing a site embedded in time.

Here is an excerpt from Smithson's slide lecture on Hotel Palenque (describing the image on page 5):

"This is interesting, back in the garden again. Here we have some bricks piled up with sticks sort of horizontally resting on these bricks. And they signify something. I never figured it out while I was there but it seemed to suggest some kind of impermanence. Something was about to take place. We were just kind of grabbed by it. You just really felt that any

minute something was going to happen. It was like a sign, a sign from something ageless actually.”²

Hotel Palenque stands out as a project that is only the

Robert Smithson, *Hotel Palenque 1969-72*, thirty-one chromogenic-development slides and audio recording, collection Solomon R. Guggenheim Museum, New York. © Estate of Robert Smithson.

account of a site through text and image without any physical residuum. In his narration Smithson disassembles

² Smithson, Robert and Neville Wakefield, “Insert Robert Smithson Hotel Palenque 1969–1972,” Parkett, Vol.43, 1995.

and reassembles the building in his weaving narrative account of Hotel Palenque. He describes the building in fragments rendering the structure incompressible as a whole. Smithson's account outlines a programmatic ambivalence and a spatial confusion. He calls attention to certain details describing materiality and tectonics, emphasizing the state of decay or the process of repair, illustrating the elements as a stratum of time, the temporal experience. The occupation, or often imagined occupation, of the different spaces of the hotel becomes part of the narration, provoking various associations, connections of spaces, of times, of cultures, describing a potential future. The various occupants which are engaged in the processes Smithson describes are not always human, the more-than-human plays an equally important role in revealing the potentiality of the construction, architect or user, plant or animal, even inorganic piles of rubble animate Smithson to ponder possible meanings. The occupants are inseparable from the perceptions of the processes of the ongoing transformations.

Smithson's lecture and the photos he took of Hotel Palenque became an important artwork in themselves, which have been presented in various forms and media.³ His lecture is counter to the conventional reading of architecture and site. The work is emblematic as a challenge for architecture in Smithson's intentional (mis)reading or over-interpretation of a building where organic growth and inorganic structure merge as an ever-unfinished entropic

³ Loe, Hikmet Sidney, "The Hotel Palenque: Robert Smithson's 1972 Utah Lecture," *Western Humanities Review* 68, no. 1 (Winter 2014): 68.

process. It is an undefined and uncertain process, but in this unpredictability lies for Smithson a certain emancipation. Specifically Smithson's notion of de-architecturing, which he also refers to in other projects and texts, is relevant in approaching demolition and de-construction of existing structures. De-architecturing can be understood as the process of dismantling architecture, a deconstruction to an unfinished, undetermined state, physically as well as conceptually. It is a merging of architecture with its site and environment. De-architecturization de-emphasizes architecture as static or finite object, instead it comprehends architecture as embracing change, and uncertainty and entangled with its environment. It transfers the aspect of space and assimilates the element of time.

Smithson's particular reading and retelling of the site and the building of Hotel Palenque offer a productive means of approaching an existing construction in architecture. Viewing the processes of deterioration and decay as generative proffers a more sensitive approach to embrace the existing with a dynamic view of the design process. As an illustration, what follows is my descriptive narration of the renovation project Schmitz, done in collaboration with Sander Rutgers and Olivier Goethals, relating the project and the process in the manner of Robert Smithson's lecture on Hotel Palenque.

This is a photo of the found condition of the building before the renovation. Schmitz is a typical townhouse built in Brussels in the early twentieth century. A rear shed was quickly demolished and a storage building was added. Later the entire ground floor was cleared and converted to a car repair shop, with over the years additional adaptations, removals, and expansions.

Intermittent openings let light enter the dark and cavernous interior of the ground floor garage—one long space extending from the street with various interruptions—the space seems to expand and contract.

Schmitz, 2017 (image credit: Bertrand Cavalier)

The structure became a self-built bricolage of different material assemblies layered over the years: concrete, bricks, steel, wood, seemingly random, depending on availability. The building was empty for over twenty years and left in a state of abandonment. A broken roof allows new life to emerge in places and new spatial qualities reveal themselves. The inside becomes an outside, a kind of enclosed garden.

Here is a good view of the storage space, above the garage. It was probably used for keeping various auto parts. It's a very functional space. Slender columns support the ceiling, defining an aisle along the center. A fractured path shows the way, but leads nowhere. Spectral light filters in and moss is starting to pervade the space. There is an ambiguous quality, neither entirely deterioration, nor regeneration. An incidental landscape of transformation emerges.

Now here is an interesting photo from the construction process. The new project takes its inspiration from the conditions of the site. It follows a logic of continuous transformation and reconstruction. Entropic change is the agent that defines the process. Windows are cut haphazardly into the existing walls to fit the new use. New bricks are added to finish the openings, layered on top and over older bricks. Construction scaffolding appears where floors are demolished, creating temporary platforms of connection between the buildings in the newly opened courtyards.

Schmitz, 2021 (image credit: Bertrand Cavalier)

Here is the new top floor. It's pushed backward to create a roof terrace. Open and free of the neighboring buildings, exposed. Yet, the architecture doesn't manifest itself. It participates in its own denudation. As if still under construction new scaffolding climbs the walls from the courtyard. Old and new merge under a stratum of paint. The aggregation of past and present is legible in the cracks of textures and patterns. Climbing plants will one day add another layer and envelope the building.

The renovation is essentially complete. Here a new roofless interior is made. Quoting Smithson referring to Hotel Palenque: “It’s a ‘de-architecturization’ you might say. It’s a breaking away of unnecessary floors.”⁴ And a rebuilding of platforms and stairs that lead to the open sky. The deconstruction and reconstruction process continues. Scaffolding partially fills spaces once occupied by floors and walls. New brick volumes replace the former garage space with its various alterations. A fragmented pathway leads through the now outdoor space of the ground floor, soon to be overgrown. The entropic ruinations of the past are continued. The project refers to a continuum of time.

⁴ Robert Smithson and Neville Wakefield, “Insert Robert Smithson Hotel Palenque 1969–1972”, Parkett, Vol.43, 1995.

The remnants of a massive bridge from the car repair shop hang above the rear courtyard. Held in place by a new beam balancing on a single concrete column, simultaneously connected to and severed from the site and the past. The building becomes the site becomes the process. Its present and the past merge and define continuity between past and present into the future. Here time becomes legible.

This is a recent photo of the project. The garden is starting to grow, a combination of planted and ruderal plants. The architecture becomes both a scaffolding and a backdrop. Plants move up, along and out. The decay of “the past folds into the present in indeterminate ways.”⁵ The distinction between building and site begins to erode.

To quote Smithson again: “I think things just change from one situation to the next, there’s really no return.”⁶

5 Caitlin DeSilvey, *Curated Decay: Heritage beyond Saving* (Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press, 2017), 183.

6 Robert Smithson, “Entropy Made Visible (1973). Interview with Alison Sky,” in Robert Smithson. *The Collected Writings*, ed. Jack Flam (Berkeley: University of California Press, 1996), 309.

Reading an existing context as Smithson does, paying attention to the detritus and the damaged, the influence of time, as well as the sometimes haphazard attempts at renewal, broadens the perception, and acceptance, of the existing construction and admits the entropic processes of deterioration into the vocabulary of architecture as a revealing and useful evolution. Decay is not only meaningful as a discursive device to analyze and theorize the built environment, highlighting the processes of change and adaptation. Smithson's notion of de-architecturing, of understanding architecture not as a static object but part of a dynamic ongoing (destructive) process, is also relevant as a design approach when dealing with existing structures. It allows the design process to embrace the fragmentary and the unfinished, to elaborate this and accept further fragments to be added as well as removed, without formalizing it.

The narrative description of a context, in the case of Schmitz of a building site, is integral to the design process, the retelling itself is part of the entropic process. The meandering account destabilizes a fixed and finite understanding of the site, assimilating the processes of the site, towards a sharing of the "entropic experience".⁷ A de-architecturing then occurs both on the site and through the narration.

De-architecturing architecture doesn't look for a final outcome, it is neither total destruction nor complete

⁷ Jacques Leenhardt, "Sur l'entropie et le paysage : à propos de Robert Smithson," *Images re-vues* Hors-série 5 | 2016, Après le tournant iconique.

renewal. It seeks the space and the time in-between, and accepts the intrusion of the elements, organic and non-organic, human and non-human, towards an ongoing process of irreversible change.

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